

THERMAL MANAGEMENT OF EDGE-COOLED 1 KW PORTABLE PROTON EXCHANGE MEMBRANE FUEL CELL STACK

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ABSTRACT

In order to study thermal management influence on the performance of 1kW edge-cooled proton exchange membrane fuel cell stack without external humidification comprehensive numerical analyses are conducted. Two numerical approaches are considered and compared for a prescribed load profile: (i) lumped model and novel (ii) real-time transient computational fluid dynamics model incorporating realistic modeling of forced air convection on the edge-cooling of the stack. The developed computational fluid dynamics model is used to study the influence of (i) bipolar plate materials (ii) operating delta pressure along the flow field and (iii) different cooling fin configurations on the water and heat balance inside the stack. The results indicate that (i) maximal and average temperatures of the stack are almost linearly correlated to the thermal conductivity of bipolar plate materials and maximal temperatures can be significantly higher (ii) the operating delta pressure can be manipulated to increase the performance of the stack and (iii) the cooling fin redesign has major influence on the overall temperature uniformity across the stack. Additionally, the heat transfer between the stack and metal hydride tank is studied.

Keywords: PEM fuel cell, Portable stack, Water and heat management

INTRODUCTION

Air-cooled proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell stacks are gaining momentum as power sources for portable applications such as electric bikes, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), forklifts, etc. Usually the power of portable stacks (PS) is up to several kW [1,2]. Most of the heat generated during PS operation is dissipated into the surrounding atmosphere via forced air convection along the cooling channels or edge-cooling fins, while the higher power stacks require liquid cooling. The emphasis during the design phase of PS is primarily directed towards determining the most suitable material for bipolar plates and the accompanying thermal management. Some of the thermal management objectives are: (i) ensuring the appropriate heat transfer from the stack during startup, i.e. accurately determining the required convection flow rate, to achieve sufficiently high operating temperature from startup at ambient temperature, thus preventing flooding (occurring if the flow rate is high and temperature of the stack is low) or membrane dehydration (occurring if the flow rate is low and temperature inside the stack is high); (ii) ensuring sufficiently high heat removal rates via forced air convection during the operation characterized by stable temperature of the stack, i.e. loosely termed steady-state operation; (iii) ensuring as low as possible temperature difference between the inside and outside portions of the stack by choosing the materials with favorable thermal properties; (iv) properly design the stack and edge-cooling fins to ensure sufficiently high heat removal rates; (v) design the frame for the stack which will ensure that the cooling air is directed to uniformly flow along the edge-cooling fins. In previous studies [3,4] it was shown that the operating temperature inside PEM fuel cell is highly non-uniform and it is not accurate to represent the operating temperature with just one parameter, while at the same time if the temperature profile is controlled it can be exploited to result in high performance of the cell by manipulating the water vapor saturation profile, i.e. relative humidity profile inside the cell. The main contributions of this work to the research field are evident in outlining that the commonly used lumped models can be misleading for dynamic analysis of PEM fuel cell performance due to inability to accurately calculate the maximal temperature inside the stack and this work also outlines under which circumstances the lumped models can be used. This work also presents a novel transient CFD model for analysis of thermal management of PS which gives insight in mass and heat transfer both inside and outside of the cell (internal heat and mass transfer and forced air convection edge-cooling), while other works focus on only one aspect and simplify the other to a significant extent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The stack used in this study, Figure 1, was developed by Proton Energy Systems. The stack displays many innovative features including in-flow configuration, cooling and stack clamping. It consists of 60 cells, each with an active area of 65

cm². The design is rectangular with 10:1 aspect ratio to allow for efficient heat conduction of the edge of the cells, where fins are extended for cooling.

Figure 1. Above: Proton Energy System's short stack exploded view (left) with annotated parts and assembly (right); Middle: Proton Energy System's 1-kW fuel-cell stack (left) and transparent shroud assembly (right); Below: Cathode (left) and anode (right) flow fields with annotated air-coolant flow direction along the edge-cooling fins.

The bipolar plates including the fins are fabricated from a molded polymer/graphite mixture (made by SGL Carbon) with effective thermal conductivity of $20 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The stack is cooled by air flow along the longer edge of the cells where the fins are located.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the lumped model and CFD analysis are shown in Figure [5]. The cell temperature increases from ambient to steady-state shows similar trends, although the lumped model predicts slightly lower steady-state temperature. The CFD data also indicates that the temperature fluctuations are always present due to the unsteady nature of the flow and modeling of the air as ideal gas, resulting in convective flow and vortex genesis in the wake region behind the stack. The temperature decrease after 5500 s reaches higher minimal value in the CFD model vs. lumped model, and after increasing the current the temperature oscillations of the CFD model are more severe and it can be noted that the steady-state predicted by the lumped model near ca. 10000 s is not yet steady-state when CFD model is observed. The highest difference between the lumped model vs. CFD model is evident after 10000 seconds by comparing the 3 cases. For case (i) the steady-state temperature of the cell in the CFD model is decreased at a slower rate when compared to the lumped model and converges to a significantly higher steady-state value (by ca. $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), and similarly also in case (ii). In case (iii) the fan must be turned on and off approx. 6 times more frequent to keep the stack temperature between the 55 and $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ range. The differences are a result of directly calculating the heat transfer coefficient in the CFD analysis vs. fixing the value in the lumped model and a result of modeling the complex flow involving air as ideal gas in the CFD model. Regardless of the differences, it can be noted that the average temperatures predicted by the lumped model and

time to reach steady-state are reasonably well predicted by the lumped model but the CFD model is more physically valid therefore it will be used in the following chapters for more detailed analysis.

Figure 2. History of cell temperature: lumped model vs. CFD for cases (i), (ii) and (iii).

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn from this work:

- (i) although commonly used, the lumped model is not accurate for predicting the temperature of the edge-cooled stacks due to the capability for only predicting the average temperature of the stack, while the maximal temperature can be several tens of degrees higher inside the stack when materials with low thermal conductivity are used, thus leading to severe dehydration of the membrane;
- (ii) by comparing the average and maximal temperature of the stack for different bipolar plate materials, it can be seen that the outside temperature of the stack is quite similar for graphite (thermal conductivity $20 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and nickel (thermal conductivity $91.74 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), i.e. $57.53 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ vs $52.41 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, during steady-state operation, while the internal maximal temperature of the stack is significantly different ($77.36 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ vs. $58.29 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively), indicating the requirement for carefully determining the appropriate material to be used for production of bipolar plates for edge-cooled stacks;
- (iii) higher pressure drop along the flow field can be used as a supplementary method for achieving higher performance of the stack since the water vapor saturation profile is pressure-dependent, or the whole stack can be operated at elevated pressure to increase the performance;
- (iv) the edge-cooling fin geometry has significant influence on the overall temperature distribution, by redesigning the edge-cooling fins the maximal temperature and average temperature of the stack was reduced from $77.60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $57.53 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $63.55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $46.57 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, indicating the necessity for careful design of the flow distributors for edge-cooling portable stacks;
- (v) the developed CFD model can also be used to study the heat transfer between the stack and MH tank. Although the heat generated by the stack was not sufficient to release the required mass flow rate of hydrogen for stack operation at 1 kW power, which was also experimentally demonstrated using similar power air-cooled stack (Nexa 1.2 kW) where 3 MH tanks were used and in that case it was possible to release the required amount of hydrogen from the tanks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors of this work would like to acknowledge the support received from the EU Horizon 2020/RISE project “Hydrogen fuelled utility vehicles and their support systems utilising metal hydrides—HYDRIDE4MOBILITY, Project Number: 778307.

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